

Impact of Visual Merchandising on Impulse Purchase of Biscuits from Reliance Smart Outlets across Palakkad City

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Abstract : This study delves into the intricate connection between impulse purchase behavior and visual merchandising, with biscuits serving as the focal point for investigation. It thoroughly examines diverse facets of visual merchandising and its potent role in captivating customers and stimulating sales. The interrelationship between the variables is substantiated through rigorous application of Chi-Square tests. Impulse purchase is contingent upon the initial allure that evokes a customer's interest at the moment of purchase.

Keywords-Visual Merchandising, Impulse Purchase, Buying Behaviour, Kerala, Biscuit

JEL Classification Number : M37,M20

1.Introduction

Consumers engage in purchasing goods from stores, whether through planned or unplanned decisions. These retail establishments witness the daily sale of numerous items, and customers acquire them based on their income levels. The frequency and quantity of store visits for purchasing goods are directly tied to individuals' financial resources. Interestingly, buyers often find themselves purchasing items they had not originally intended to, a phenomenon commonly referred to as impulse buying. Abratt and Goodey (1990) emphasized the global significance of studying impulse purchases in supermarkets, highlighting its relevance to both manufacturers and retailers. Sagini Thomas Mathai (2014) further explains that each individual possesses a distinctive personality and behaviour pattern, contributing to their unique consumer behavior. These psychological attributes play a substantial role in shaping consumers' decision-making processes during the act of purchasing.

Visual merchandising in food retailing, on the other hand, remains relatively unstudied and under-practiced because small margins in the food category frequently necessitate strict cost control, which leads to neglect of visual merchandising. At the same time, food stores require good store design and visual merchandising in particular because they sell the majority of merchandise that is readily available in other stores and heavily depend on self-

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service *Ivana Štulec* (et al. 2016 Today's retailers face the challenge of keeping expenses under control while meeting the ever-increasing demands of their customers. To accomplish both objectives, they are forced to maximize retail space utilization, that is to maximize sales per square meter of retail space.

The history of biscuits in India dates back to the early 1900s when the British ruled over India. Biscuits were introduced by the British to Indians as a snack for tea time. The Indian biscuit industry appears to be the largest among all food industries and has a limited profit margin of Rs. 300 billion. The sheer size of the market has made sure a steady rise of new entrants into an already competitive field. To stand apart from other brands that share the shelf space in a retail store, they must deploy strategies to get attention from potential customers. This study focuses on understanding the effectiveness of visual merchandising specifically towards Impulse buying Behaviour. Posters, Instore Displays, and Pop-Up shelves are the various dimensions of visual merchandising that were identified inside the stores

According to the 'Indian Biscuit Market Overview report 2017-23' The organized biscuit market accounts for more than 70% of value in the overall Indian biscuit market. The sector might cross the revenue figure of INR 400 billion by 2023. Big brands such as Parle, Britannia, and Unibic are involved in the market by providing different product categories of biscuits such as cream sandwich, cookies, glucose, Marie gold, crackers, milk, digestive, and other novelty biscuits.

Reliance Smart points are widely spread across Palakkad and are getting good footfalls that averaged about 200-400 customers a day and the results trend towards a finding that customers tend to purchase newly arrived biscuit brands from the awareness created by the various visual merchandising deployments in store.

A welcoming atmosphere in a store is a very promising degree of stimulator and a simple structure that, while being cognitively "calming," also highly activates important artifacts that, on the other hand, aid in the formation of mental store maps. Visual merchandising, broadly speaking, refers to everything a consumer sees, both inside and out. The store's exterior design should reflect the interior and atmosphere inside, enticing prospective customers inside. The floor plan of the stores was almost identical and the only differentiation being the store size. On primary inspection it was found that lighting fixtures were the same in all stores across Palakkad.

2.Statement of The Problem

Impulse purchase is very common in the FMCG market place. In the location of study, a chain of supermarket is identified and the relationship between how visual merchandising

techniques affects impulse buying is to be studied. Biscuit industry is highly competitive and brands are being introduced into the market in a weekly basis. So how new brands or the existing giants such as ITC and Britannia gain competitive advantage through visual merchandising needs to be looked upon closely.

The researcher made sure to also consider brand loyalty and brand perception of the respondents while purchasing. Since the research is done based on the impulse model of purchase, the customer is not expected to dwell deep into considering the pros and cons of the purchase.

3.Objectives

- To identify the visual merchandising factors influencing impulse buying behaviour.
- To analyse the effect of visual merchandising on impulse buying behaviour
- To identify the relationship (if any between impulse buying and visual merchandising).

4.CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 Source Kim, J. (2003. College students' apparel impulse buying behaviours in relation to visual merchandising.

Figure 2 Iberahim, Hadijah & Zulkurnain, Nur & Raja, Ainal & Rosli, Siti & Mara, University & Alam, Shah. (2019. Visual Merchandising and Customers' Impulse Buying Behavior: A Case of a Fashion Specialty Store.

5.Limitations

- This study was exclusively conducted within the city of Palakkad. Cultural and Sociographic factors might differ from various other cities.
- The research was focused solely on how customers purchase biscuits. The results might not be applicable to the other impulse purchase products.

- Brand perception and advertising can also affect impulse buying but those 2 factors are overlooked while giving their instore perception more importance.
- The researcher also encountered some problems while collecting data since Palakkad is the largest district in the state of Kerala and many of them were not aware about Reliance Smart Outlets

6. Review of Literature

Many researchers have done some incredible work when it comes to the various visual merchandising techniques and its overall effectiveness on the customers. Some of their research show that Visual merchandising offers the customers good physical evidence and acts as a silent salesman for the product. The purpose of visual merchandising is to inform customers, improve the store's and company's image, and support extensive product grouping and accessory display says *Silayoi & Speece 2007*. An anonymous source from FERRERO India Private Limited informed that getting shelf space in supermarkets is a hassle and adding the merchandise effectively to increase visibility is key to driving sales as well as getting customer attention.

Technology and the media boom have caused a rise of savvy customers who know about various brand their point of parities as well as their point of differences. Impulse buying requires little to no buying decision process, Customer See, Customer Interacts and Customer Buys. Retailers can use visual merchandising tools to direct the customer's attention towards the products that are on sale. The previous research studies primarily focused on apparel and fashion industry, but FMCG sales can also be boosted through Visual Merchandising and through impulse buying it can also bring in a considerable rate of new customers.

6.1 Impulse Buying Behaviour

1. *Beatty and Ferrell (1998 "Concepts of Impulse Purchases"*. Defined impulse purchases are those made without any pre-shopping goals, whether to acquire a specific product category or to meet a specific need. They outlined how shoppers experience impulse purchasing behaviour, which happens quickly and without much thought. The purchase of an out-of-stock object when reminded while shopping for it is not considered to be an impulse purchase.
2. According to Block, L. G., & Morwitz, V. G. (1999). Shopping lists as an external memory aid for grocery shopping: Influences on list writing and list fulfilment. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 8(4), 343–375. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327663jcp0804_01 an impulse purchase is one made by a

customer as a result of an intense desire that strikes them suddenly and without much thought.

3. *Iyer* (1989 “Relationship between impulsive purchases and unplanned purchases”. went on to point out that while all impulsive purchases are unplanned, not all unplanned purchases are done through impulse purchase behaviour.
4. *Han et al.* (1991 modified the *Stern* (1962 classification of impulse mix in relation to fashion products and developed four impulse purchase models.
 - i Planned impulse buying
 - ii Reminded impulse buying
 - iii Suggestion or fashion-oriented impulse buying
 - iv Pure impulse buying

There are three major schools of thought in academic research that examines the different impulse buying triggers.

5. *Verplanken and Herabadi* (2001 contend that certain personality characteristics cause people to make impulsive purchases. Marketing cues or stimuli that are put and managed by the marketer in an effort to entice customers into purchasing behaviour are referred to as external factors of impulse buying. (*Youn and Faber*, 2000).
6. Five key factors are identified by *Rook and Hock* (1983 as contributing to the urge to buy rather than on finding a solution in impulse buying: a sudden and spontaneous desire to solve a problem already present or on finding an object to complete an act, a psychological state of disequilibrium, the onset of predetermined need. Last but not least, impulsive buying immediately decreases in line with general psychological conflict and confusion.
7. *Rettie & Brewer*, (2000 defines that Self-service packaging, which is becoming more popular, positions itself as a "salesman" on the shelf and serves as a vehicle for communication and promotion. The packaging must guarantee customer reaction to the product and must have the ability to attract and persuade a potential customer to make the purchase. Essentially curiosity and desire also drive motive to buy products impulsively. Purchase decisions, particularly impulsive ones, can be influenced by a variety of consumer variables. The customer has a shopping experience as a result of their impulsive purchase behaviour. Hedonic shopping value can be applied to this event.
8. *Meenakumari* (2013 took into account a number of crucial visual merchandising elements, such as the entrance, advertising signage, window display, fixtures, floor area, and interiors. She discovered that each of these elements significantly affected the

likelihood of a spontaneous buy. *Bhatti and Latif* (2014) investigated the effects of visual merchandising on impulse buying, looking at storefront display, brand name, floor merchandising, and forum display. They discovered that visual marketing has a significant impact on impulsive decisions.

9. Visual marketing and impulse buying are related in a structural way, according to a model put forth by *Moayery, Zamanl, and Vazlfeedoost* (2014). They discovered that while cross merchandising and floor merchandising had a minimal effect on impulse purchases of apparel, storefront display, mannequin display, and promotional signage did.
10. Visual merchandising elements like shop layout, colour, lighting, cleanliness, and store design were taken into account by *Kouchejian and Gharibpoor* (2012). They discovered that visual merchandising had a big influence on people making impulsive purchases.
11. Visual merchandising is store presentation, along with its merchandise, through the store's advertising, display, special events, fashion coordination and merchandising departments in order to sell goods and services (*Astrid & Mustika*, 2013). The authors point out that the store uses visual merchandising as a tool to increase product visibility.
12. According to *Ortega-S* (2011), visual merchandising can help shoppers understand the worth and calibre of a store's fashion offerings. The goals of visual merchandising are to draw people, improve the store's appearance, and boost sales; it also states that to draw customers and promote impulsive or unplanned purchase, every area, setting, and visual aspect of visual merchandising, focused on the shop's sign boards, mood, shelf layout, section divisions, and cleanliness, is set up.
13. *Jalees, Tariq, Kazmi, Syed Hasnain Alam and Zaman, Syed Imran*. "The Effect of Visual Merchandising, Sensational Seeking and Collectivism on Impulsive Buying Behaviour" *Journal of Systems Science and Information*, vol. 4, no. 4, 2016, pp. 321-333. <https://doi.org/10.21078/JSSI-2016-321-13> found that Sensationalism and impulsive buying were found to be strongly and positively correlated, but collectivism and impulsive buying, as well as visual merchandising and impulsive buying, were not. One of the study's contributions is that it examined previously understudied links between collectivism, sensationalism, and impulsive purchasing.
14. *Kim, Jiyeon*. "College students' apparel impulse buying behaviours in relation to visual merchandising." (2003). Their findings demonstrate a significant correlation between college students' impulse buying tendencies and two types of visual merchandising techniques: in-store form/mannequin display and promotional signage.

15. Mr. Chand Saini, Ms. Rakhi Gupta and Mr. Ishant Khurana ” Visual Merchandising And Impulse Buying Behavior: A Case Of Retail Industry” *ijarse*, Vol. No.4, Special Issue (02, February 2015 states that Visual merchandising techniques undoubtedly affect clients' purchasing decisions and trigger impulse purchases. According to the findings, the following themes were most strongly associated with purchase intention: product colours, presentation style, awareness of fixtures, pathfinding, sensory properties of materials, and lighting

Research methodology

The study's goal is to determine how various elements of visual merchandising affect consumers' impulsive purchases of biscuits at Reliance smart points scattered throughout Palakkad district. An organized questionnaire was used to gather the data. The respondents' propensity for making impulsive purchases was assessed in the first part of the questionnaire. A quick purchase choice, no imminent need for the product, and a specific customer's reaction to in-store stimuli are the three criteria that make a purchase unplanned, according to the literature review. A sample size of 150 Reliance Smart point customers was chosen at random for the study. The questionnaire also included several questions that will assess the respondent's opinion about the overall store layout and other elements of visual merchandising. The location of study is the District of Palakkad.

SOURCES OF DATA

Primary data was collected through a detailed questionnaire which had relevant objective type questions regarding customers awareness about visual merchandising, their shopping trends, their brand preferences (if any towards a specific biscuit brand as well as their impulse buying motives. A random sample of 150 respondents were taken for the study at a ratio of 30 customers per outlet (5 Outlets in Palakkad city
Secondary data was collected from various E journals, Magazines and websites.

TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

The main sources were the questionnaire, but while the occasional visits to the smart outlets led to some personal interviews with their customer where the researcher was able to identify their personal motives behind making specific purchases.

Analysis and interpretation

Chi-Square analysis(X^2)

$$\text{Formula - } X^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E$$

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected Frequency

$E = (\text{Row Total} * \text{column Total} / \text{Grand total})$

Degree of freedom = $(r - 1) * (c - 1)$

Null and alternative hypothesis

(H₀ NULL HYPOTHESIS: There is no significant relationship between the customer being attracted by the various attractive displays and their impulsiveness in purchase

(H₁ ALTERNATE HYPOTHESIS: There is significant relationship between the customer being attracted by the various attractive displays and their impulsiveness in purchase.

TABLE OF OBSERVED VALUES

Attractiveness towards Displays	Impulsiveness					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
Strongly Agree	0	0	4	3	17	24
Agree	0	9	24	6	4	43
Neutral	0	9	20	8	4	41
Disagree	1	7	18	0	0	26
Strongly Disagree	16	0	0	0	0	16
Total	17	25	66	17	25	150

TABLE OF EXPECTED VALUES

Attractiveness towards Displays	Impulsiveness				
	1	2	3	4	5
Strongly Agree	2.72	4	10.56	2.72	4
Agree	4.87	7.17	18.92	4.87	7.17
Neutral	4.65	6.83	18.04	4.65	6.83
Disagree	2.95	4.33	11.44	2.95	4.33
Strongly Disagree	1.81	2.67	7.04	1.81	2.67

From the observed and expected table the χ^2 value has been deduced as **213.2426**.

Degree of Freedom = $(r - 1) * (c - 1)$

we have 5 rows and 5 columns, so

Degree of Freedom = $(5 - 1) * (5 - 1) = 4 * 4 = \mathbf{16}$.

At significance level of 0.05 and 16 degrees of freedom, the critical chi-square value is **26.296**.

Since the calculated value is higher than the table value the null hypothesis is rejected.

Which in turn leads to the acceptance of the alternate hypothesis which stated **(H1** There is significant relationship between the customer being attracted by the various attractive displays and their impulsiveness in purchase.

Chi-Square analysis(χ^2 II

(H0: There is no significant relationship between spontaneous purchase decisions and offers/discounts in the store

(H1: There is significant relationship between spontaneous purchase decisions and offers/discounts in the store

TABLE OF OBSERVED VALUES

Spontaneous Decision	Purchase according to Offers					Total
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
Strongly Agree	16	14	0	0	0	30
Agree	12	22	8	0	0	42
Neutral	17	26	6	7	4	60
Disagree	0	7	0	0	4	11
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	7	7
Total	45	69	14	7	15	150

TABLE OF EXPECTED VALUES

Spontaneous Decision	Offers and Discounts				
	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Strongly Agree	9	13.8	2.8	1.4	3
Agree	12.6	19.32	3.92	1.96	4.2
Neutral	18	27.6	5.6	2.8	6
Disagree	3.3	5.06	1.0267	0.5133	1.1
Strongly Disagree	2.1	3.22	0.6533	0.3267	0.7

From the observed and expected table the χ^2 value has been deduced as **105.2333**

At significance level of 0.05 and 16 degrees of freedom, the critical chi-square value is **26.296**.

Since the calculated value is higher than the table value the null hypothesis is rejected.

Which in turn leads to the acceptance of the alternate hypothesis which stated

(H1: There is significant relationship between spontaneous purchase decisions and offers/discounts in the store

Findings

- The study revealed that visual merchandising and impulse buying behaviour are interrelated.
- The study shows that customers make purchase decisions after seeing the various offers and discounts displayed through the shop.
- The study also showed that 72.5 percent of respondents visit Smart outlets once a week for their shopping
- Britannia was found to be the most favoured (57.5 % brand among other brands.
- The study also showed that customers exhibit more impulse behaviour if the shop has attractive visual merchandising displays.
- 45 percentage of the respondents purchase biscuits for their pets, which is not done impulsively.
- 46 percentage of respondents agreed that their shopping experience is enhanced by the store ambience
- Packaging was preferred by the majority as the number one factor that rives impulse buying behaviour
- The study also found that counter displays in supermarket saw the highest impulse purchases

Suggestions

- Visual displays have stood the test of time as a way of attracting customers in store, Signage and Flex boards pose the threat of waste accumulation. Green visual merchandising can be followed.
- Reliance Smart outlets have been witnessing a rapid surge in their expansion, and their consistent and commendable standard layout is noteworthy. However, it is crucial to address the aspect of product availability and stock management to ensure more effective operations.
- Reliance Smart can enhance customer satisfaction, minimize instances of out-of-stock items, and ultimately improve the overall shopping experience.
- Biscuits are a snack commodity preferred by children and adults alike, the visual merchandising of brands must cater to all ages.
- Biscuits can be kept near the cash counter to drive impulse buying of biscuits.
- Upkeeping of shelves and removal of dust and debris can be done periodically as part of maintenance
- Signs that show offers and discounts must be removed once the offer period runs out to avoid miscommunication

- Shopping has become a hedonistic pleasure; hence visual merchandising also must become a crutch that adds to the experience

Conclusion

Visual merchandising is an exquisite technique that accentuates the art of crafting visually alluring and captivating displays, meticulously orchestrated to elevate the presentation and enhance the overall shopping experience within retail establishments and similar physical settings. This refined practice involves thoughtfully curating and exhibiting merchandise, fixtures, signage, and other visual elements, with the primary objective of enticing customers, effectively communicating the brand's distinct identity, and ultimately engendering a surge in sales. Impulse buying behavior, on the other hand, alludes to the proclivity of consumers to engage in unplanned and spontaneous purchases, devoid of prior intention or meticulous contemplation.

According to the customers who were sampled in the study, Visual merchandising and impulse buying have a significant relationship. This was proved by both chi 2 tests conducted

When it comes to the purchase of biscuits, multiple factors exert influence on impulse buying behavior. The artful blend of eye-catching packaging and alluring displays assumes a pivotal role in eliciting impulsive purchases. Lively hues, captivating designs, and prominent positioning of biscuit assortments possess the power to seize the attention of shoppers, effectively tantalizing them into making spur-of-the-moment decisions. Placing biscuits strategically in close proximity to checkout counters or within bustling thoroughfares can notably heighten the probability of impulsive buying. As consumers chance upon conveniently situated biscuit selections, they may succumb to the temptation of swiftly adding a pack or two to their shopping carts, often without considerable deliberation. This study elucidated the profound impact of visual merchandising on the impulse purchase of biscuits, with Reliance Smart outlets situated across Palakkad selected as the designated locations for data collection and analysis.

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